

Students' & Teachers' Attitude towards New Curriculum of Life Science at Secondary Level in West Bengal

Wasim Mallick¹, Ujjwal Paul² and Abhijit Guha³

¹M.Phil Research Scholar, Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira, Belur Math, Howrah
E-mail: wasimmallick87@gmail.com

²Assistant Professor, Government College of Education (C.T.E.), Banipur, North 24 Parganas,
E-mail: ujjwalpaulss9@gmail.com

³Assistant Professor(Sr.), Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira, Belur Math, Howrah
E-mail: abhi.guha68@gmail.com

ABSTRACT : Curriculum should be based upon totality of experiences, variety & flexibility, relation to community life, training for leisure and integration and correlation (Secondary Education Commission -1952-53) and curriculum framework which should contain a common core along with other components which are flexible (NPE-1986). Science curriculum should be strengthened so as to develop in the child well-defined abilities and values such as the spirit of inquiry, creativity, objectives, the courage to question and an aesthetic sensibility and Science education programs will be designed to enable the learner to acquire problem solving ability, experimental skills and to discover the relationship of science with health, agriculture, industry and other aspects of daily life (NPE-1986). In West Bengal new science curriculum was constructed on the basis of above mentioned objectives with constructivist approach(NCF-2005) in teaching learning and it was implemented from 2013 at Upper Primary along with other levels of schooling. The present study was conducted to inquire the students' and teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science at secondary level in West Bengal. SATNCLS andTATNCLS were administered into 100 randomly selected students and 60 randomly selected life science teachers for measuring their attitude towards new curriculum of life science in WBBSE.The major findings were observed that students and life science teachers of West Bengal possess a moderate positive attitude towards new life science curriculum. Female students had better attitude towards life science new curriculum than male and on the other hand rural students have higher attitude towards life science new curriculum than the urban student. Another most important finding was male teacher possessed higher attitude towards new curriculum of life science than female teachers, but location of school, academic qualification and training had no significant role to construct attitude of teachers towards new curriculum of life science.

Keywords : Teachers' Attitude, Students' Attitude, Life Science New Curriculum, Secondary Level, West Bengal

Introduction

Curriculum is the soul of the process of education system. It acts as a pivot in organizing educational effort on some manageable basis and is undoubtedly the heart of the school and all that goes with it. It is futile to take how and when without first deciding what to teach.

According to John Dewey (1902) “Curriculum is a continuous reconstruction, moving from the child’s present experience out into that represented by the organized bodies of truth that we call studies . . . the various studies . . . are themselves experience— they are that of the race”. (pp. 11–12)

To define the aim of the curriculum, Henkel &Kogan (1999) find it convenient to distinguish between programs designed to satisfy “academic” objectives and those designed to satisfy “vocational” objectives and they find two models for curriculum *organization*. Emphasis on academic objectives tends to lead to the “individualistic” curriculum, characterized by a loose coupling of subjects, choice for students and staff, and little concern for vocational skills. “Staffs are free to offer options whether or not they link with other elements of the curriculum: these will typically follow research interests. Curriculum development is . . . discipline-led, incremental, strongly influenced by student demand and staff preference.” Conversely, emphasis on employment objectives tends to lead to the “directed” curriculum, with an emphasis on course design and coherence. Henkel &Kogan (1999) observe that “teachers’ freedom is limited since courses must link in a coherent way. Curriculum development is . . . course-led, systematic, and less influenced by individual objectives.”

While preparing to design and implement an instructional improvement program — planning change — independent school educators need to acknowledge a faculty’s right to have three understandings made clear from the very start of the process: *Why is a change necessary? What are we changing to? How will we get there?* (Evans, 2004) The answers to these questions will vary from school to school, but in addressing the first one, Lois Hetland of the Harvard Graduate School of Education puts it compellingly as follows:

Learning something new means questioning those things we do well automatically. It means questioning our tacit expertise....It is the willingness to risk some clumsy movements that allows us to become explicit and intentional about what we do. And that, as far as I can tell, is how we can best honor the mystery of learning in our teaching (1996).

In this spirit, the goal for faculty members is to create conversations about what students and teachers (in that order) need from instructional design and delivery, and how they can best be enriched and challenged throughout the course of their experience at the school through structuring and delivering curriculum and instruction. Administrators and teacher leaders charged with facilitating successful change measures will necessarily strive to remain relentlessly optimistic about the outcomes of the reflective review process, while both anticipating and respecting some mistakes and frustration, which are natural aspects of the change experience.

In West Bengal the State Government had constituted a Committee on Experts under notification No.849-SE(S)/ES/S/10M-64/11

dated 20.7.2011 with subsequent Notification nos. 902-SE(S)/ES/S/IOM-64/11 dated 4.8.2011, 1006-SE(S)/ES/SI10M-64/11 dated 30.8.2011, 1561-SE(S)/ES/S/IOM-64/11, dated 15.12.2011 and 16-SE(S) / ES/S/IOM-64/11 dated 02.01.2012 to examine the entire syllabi, curricula and texts from Class-I to Class-XU in West Bengal and to suggest modifications thereof in line with the provisions of Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009, National Curriculum Framework - 2005 & 2009.

West Bengal Council of Higher Secondary Education, West Bengal Board of Secondary Education and West Bengal Board of Primary Education were therefore requested to immediately reconstitute their Syllabus Committee so that the respective Syllabus Committee with the active guidance, help and advice of the Expert Committee would revise the syllabi and curricula and texts in line with the recommendations of the Expert Committee. The State Government also accepted the recommendations of the Expert Committee that the curricula, syllabi and texts for Classes I, III, V, VII, IX and XI were to be revised and rewritten as per recommendations of the Expert Committee immediately so that the revised syllabi, curricula and texts would become effective from the academic session 2013. This exercise was to start immediately and completed by July 2012 so that the revised text books would be printed well ahead of the academic session 2013.

The lack of skill and knowledge in science teaching is related to teachers' attitudes about science teaching (Shrigley, 1983). The word *attitude* describes outward and observable actions relating to beliefs. Attitudes are rooted

in experience and affect what an individual will see, hear, think, and do. The outcome of attitudes is the tendency to react favorably or unfavorably to situations, persons, or events. Accordingly, teacher actions are shaped by their attitudes. Numerous studies agree on the positive correlation between science teaching attitudes and the ability to be an effective science teacher. Factors affecting teaching attitudes are found to include confidence about subject content, willingness to utilize curricular and pedagogical innovations, and a commitment to student learning (de Souza-Barros & Elia, 1997). Westerback & Long (1990) explain that teachers who are comfortable teaching science are more likely to devote more time to science teaching and will teach with more creativity. Over the years, many studies have reported that teachers who have positive attitudes about their teaching can have a significant impact on their students' achievement (Ashton, Webb, & Doda, 1983; Berman & McLaughlin, 1977; Lasserre, 1989).

So an exploration is very much needed to find out the teachers' and students' attitude towards new science curriculum in the present situation of West Bengal.

Objectives of the study

The following major objectives were identified for the study:

O₁, To study the attitude of the students about life science new curriculum at secondary level under different categorical variables.

O₂, To study the attitude of life science teachers towards new curriculum of life science at secondary level under different categorical variables like location of school, gender, academic qualification and training.

Hypotheses

H₀1: There would be no significant difference in the attitude towards new curriculum of life science between the students of rural and urban school.

H₀2: There would be no significant difference in the attitude towards new curriculum of life science among male and female students.

H₀3: There would be no significant difference in the attitude towards new curriculum of life science between the teachers of rural and urban school.

H₀4: There would be no significant difference in the attitude towards new curriculum of life science between the male and female teachers.

H₀5: There would be no significant difference in the attitude towards new curriculum of life science between the under-graduate and post-graduate teachers.

H₀6: There would be no significant difference in the attitude towards new curriculum of life science between the trained and non-trained teachers.

Methodology of the study

The present study was done through descriptive survey study i.e. it was a quantitative study. Students and life science teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science at secondary level had been analyzed quantitatively.

Sample

All the life science teachers and students of secondary school in West Bengal were the population in the study. For conducting the research, data had been collected in two phases.

Firstly 4 schools were selected conveniently from the district of Howrah and Nadia and the scale (SATNCLS) was administered to 100 students (Male/Female-50 & Rural/Urban-50) and asked to response according to their own belief and submit the response scale. In next phase 31 schools were selected randomly from the district of Nadia, North-24-Parganas, Hooghly and Howrah and the scale (TATNCLS) was administered to 60 teachers (Male/Female-30, Rural/Urban-30, Under-graduate-21, Post-graduate-39 & Trained-41, Non-trained-19) and asked to response according to their own opinion and thought without any consultation with other teacher and to submit the responded scale into an envelope for its confidentiality.

Variables

- A) Major:
- i) Students' attitude towards new curriculum of life science
 - ii) Teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science
- B) Categorical variables:
- i) Location of school
 - ii) Gender
 - iii) Qualification of teachers
 - iv) Training

Tools of the study

Present researchers had used two types of self made tools, one was attitude scale to measure the students' attitude towards new curriculum of life science (SATNCLS). Second scale was teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science (TATNCLS). The items

of both scales were checked by the experts and selected / edited according to their opinions.

Description of Students' Attitude towards New Curriculum of Life Science (SATNCLS)

Initial items of the scale were 26. After testing the reliability through Cronbach's Alpha five items were deleted for weak correlation and the scale was finally consisted of 21 items, The categories of responses were 'strongly agree', 'agree', 'undecided', 'disagree', 'strongly disagree' and '5', '4', '3', '2', '1' were the respective scores awarded for the responses. Some items were negative in nature and the scoring was done in reverse order i.e. '1', '2', '3', '4', '5'. Reliability of the scale was computed by using Cronbach's Alpha through SPSS 20.0 version and was found 0.588 and it has a good alpha value and it was acceptable.

Description of Teachers' Attitude towards New Curriculum of Life Science (TATNCLS)

Initial items of the scale were 27. After testing the reliability through Cronbach's Alpha four items were deleted for weak correlation and the scale was finally consisted of 21 items, The categories of responses were 'strongly agree', 'agree', 'undecided', 'disagree', 'strongly disagree' and '5', '4', '3', '2', '1' were the respective scores awarded for the responses. Some items were negative in nature and the

scoring was done in reverse order i.e. '1', '2', '3', '4', '5'. Reliability of the scale was computed by using Cronbach's Alpha through SPSS 20.0 version and was found 0.829 and it has a good alpha value and it was acceptable.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

The raw data were tabulated in MS Excel 2007 and analyses of data were done through SPSS 20.0 version.

Objective Wise Analysis of Data

Objective no.1

O₁. To study the attitude of the students about life science new curriculum at secondary level under different categorical variables.

To fulfill this objective, two null hypotheses were formulated and tested which were as follows:

H₀1: There would be no significant difference in the attitude towards new curriculum of life science between the students of rural and urban school.

H₀2: There would be no significant difference in the attitude towards new curriculum of life science among male and female students.

Testing of Null Hypotheses:

To test the H₀1 and H₀2 descriptive and inferential statistics were computed. The results are given below:

Table 1.1: Group Statistics of SATNCLS_location

Sub-scale	Location	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
SATNCLS	Rural	50	76.50	6.547	.926
	Urban	50	73.02	6.420	1.246

(SATNCLS= Students' attitude towards new curriculum of life science)

Table - 1.2: Independent samples test of SATNCLS _rural vs. urban

Sub-scale	Equal variances assumed	t- test equality of means		
		t	df	Sig. (2 tailed)
SATNCLS		2.242*	98	.027

(* significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Testing of Ho1:

Groups:Students of rural and urban school

Interpretation:

From the analyses in Table 1.2 it is seen that in case of students' attitude towards new curriculum of life science between rural and urban the calculated $t_{(98)}$ value is 2.242 and 'p' value is 0.027 ($p < .05$). Hence, t is significant at 0.05 level. So, Ho1 is rejected and it can be safely said that rural students are significantly different from the urban students with respect to their attitude towards new curriculum of life science.

Testing of Ho2:

Groups:Male and female students

Interpretation:

From the analyses in Table 1.4 it is seen that in case of students' attitude towards new curriculum of life science between male and female the calculated $t_{(98)}$ value is -2.406 and 'p' value is 0.018 ($p < .05$). Hence, t is significant at 0.05 levels. So, Ho2 is rejected and it can be safely said that male students are significantly different from the female students with respect to their attitude towards new curriculum of life science.

Objective no.2

O₂: To study the attitude of life science teachers towards new curriculum of life science at secondary level under different categorical variables like location of school, gender, academic qualification and training.

Table 1.3: Group Statistics of SATNCLS_gender

Sub-scale	GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
SATNCLS	Male	50	72.90	8.851	1.252
	Female	50	76.62	6.420	.908

(SATNCLS= Students' attitude towards new curriculum of life science)

Table 1.4: Independent samples test of SATNCLS _male vs. female

Sub-scale	Equal variances assumed	t- test equality of means		
		t	df	Sig. (2 tailed)
SATNCLS		-2.406*	98	.018

(* significant at 0.05 level of significance)

To fulfill this objective, two null hypotheses were formulated and tested which were as follows:

H₃: There would be no significant difference in the attitude towards new curriculum of life science between the teachers of rural and urban school.

H₄: There would be no significant difference in the attitude towards new curriculum of life science between the male and female teachers.

H₅: There would be no significant difference in the attitude towards new curriculum of life science between the under-graduate and post-graduate teachers.

H₆: There would be no significant difference in the attitude towards new curriculum of life science between the trained and non-trained teachers.

Interpretation:

During compare to the rural and urban teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science, it is seen from the analyses of Table 1.6 that in case of Levene's test for equality of variances the p value is 0.607 ($p > .05$) so, homogeneous variances can be assumed. Table 1.6 also shows that in case of teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science between rural and urban teachers the calculated $t_{(58)}$ value is 1.378 and 'p' value is 0.137 ($p > .05$). Hence, t is not significant at 0.05 level and Ho3 is not rejected. So, rural teachers are not significantly different from the urban teachers with respect to teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science.

Testing of Ho4:

Groups: Male and female life science teachers

Table – 1.5: Group Statistics of TATNCLSS_location

Sub-scale	Location	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
TATNCLS	Rural	30	79.90	10.433	1.905
	Urban	30	76.63	7.721	1.410

(TATNCLS= Teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science)

Table- 1.6: Independent samples test_TATNCLS_urban vs. rural

Sub-scale	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			t- test equality of means		
	Equal variances assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig.(2 tailed)
TATNCLS		.267	.607	1.378**	58	.173

(** not significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Testing of Ho3:

Groups: Life science teachers of urban schools and rural schools

Interpretation:

From the analyses in Table 1.8 it is seen that in case of teachers' attitude towards new

Table – 1.7: Group Statistics of TATNCLS_gender

Sub-scale	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
TATNCLS	Male	30	81.83	8.615	1.573
	Female	30	74.70	8.571	1.565

(TATNCLS= Teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science)

Table - 1.8: Independent samples test of TATNCS_male vs. female

Sub-scale	Equal variances assumed	t- test equality of means		
		t	df	Sig. (2 tailed)
TATNCLS		3.215*	58	.002

(*significant at 0.05 level of significance)

curriculum of life science between male and female the calculated $t_{(58)}$ value is 3.215 and 'p' value is 0.002 ($p < .05$). Hence, t is significant at 0.05 level. So, H_0 is rejected and it can be safely said that males are significantly different from the female teachers with respect to their attitude towards new curriculum of life science.

Testing of H_0 :

Groups: Under-graduate and post-graduate life science teachers

Interpretation:

It is seen from the analyses of Table 1.10 that in case of Levene's Test for equality of variances the p value is 0.685 ($p > .05$) so, equal

Table – 1.9: Group Statistics of TATNCLS_qualification

Sub-scale	Qualification	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
TATNCLS	Under-graduate	21	77.81	9.458	2.064
	Post-graduate	39	78.51	9.248	1.481

(TATNCLS= Teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science)

Table- 1.10: Independent samples test_TATNCLS_under-graduate vs. post-graduate

Sub-scale	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			t- test equality of means		
	Equal variances assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig.(2 tailed)
TATNCLS		0.166	0.685	-0.279**	58	0.781

(** not significant at 0.05 level of significance)

variances can be assumed. Table 1.10 also shows that in case of teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science between undergraduate and post-graduate teachers the calculated $t_{(58)}$ value is -0.279 and 'p' value is 0.781 ($p > .05$). Hence, t is not significant at 0.05 level and H_05 is not rejected. So, under-graduate teachers are not significantly different from the post-graduate teachers with respect to their attitude towards new curriculum of life science.

t is not significant at 0.05 level and H_06 is not rejected. So, trained teachers are not significantly different from the non-trained teachers with respect to their attitude towards new curriculum of life science.

Discussion

In the present study, the researchers examined students' attitudes towards life sciences. Life Sciences as a school subject is

Table – 1.11: Group Statistics of TATNCLS_training

Sub-scale	Training	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
TATNCLS	Trained	41	77.05	9.365	1.463
	Non-trained	19	80.89	8.647	1.984

(TATNCLS= Teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science)

Table- 1.12: Independent samples test_TATNCLS_trained vs. non-trained

Sub-scale	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			t- test equality of means		
	Equal variances assumed	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig.(2 tailed)
TATNCLS	Equal variances assumed	0.358	0.552	-1.515**	58	0.135

(** not significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Testing of H_06 :

Groups: Trained and non-trained life science teachers

Interpretation:

It is seen from the analyses of Table 1.12 that in case of Levene's Test for equality of variances the p value is 0.552 ($p > .05$) so, equal variances can be assumed. Table 1.12 also shows that in case of teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science between trained and non-trained teachers the calculated $t_{(58)}$ value is -1.515 and 'p' value is 0.135 ($p > .05$). Hence,

conventionally detached from other science courses in India. This study varies from the other researches for the reason that it inspects students' attitudes toward life Science, not toward science in general. Furthermore, an additional feature of this study is that, it assures to seal one of the cracks in the area related to comparing students' attitudes with respect to curricular differences and grades.

One of the important results of the study is that, gender is the major factor that impacts students' attitude toward life science. Thus, in general terms, the students have a positive

attitude toward life science new curriculum and girls have better positive attitude than boys towards new curriculum of life science. Keeves and Kotte (1992) and Jones, Howe and Rua (2000) showed that, unlike chemistry or physics, girls showed positive attitudes toward biology than boys that result support the findings of present study.

This study shows location of school or strata is the major factor that impacts students' attitude toward life science new curriculum. In this respect the rural students are significantly different than the urban students. Dosanjh (2015) found that the rural students were more closed with the flora and fauna, agricultural activity and natural environment that result support present phenomenon of the study.

This study also had measured teachers' attitude towards newly implemented life science curriculum. In case of teachers' attitude towards life science new curriculum male teachers possess more positive attitude than female teachers. National Science Foundation data (NSF, 1994) support the findings of the study.

While to search and compare the present scenario of attitude of life science teachers towards life science new curriculum at secondary level of West Bengal (W.B.) under different categorical variables it has been found from this study that teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science in urban setting are not significantly different from rural school of W.B. though, rural school teachers are slightly better than urban schools' teacher. So, it may be concluded that, the location of school or cultural settings are not the main factors for building teachers' attitude. In the same way, the present study also indicates that location of

school does not play any crucial role in construction of teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science.

In the present study attitude towards life science new curriculum of post graduate teachers are insignificantly different from under-graduate teachers though, post-graduate teachers are slightly better than under-graduate teacher. So, it may be concluded that, the academic qualification of teachers are not the main factors for building teachers' attitude. In the same way, the present study also indicates that qualification of teacher does not play any crucial role in construction of teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science.

In the present study attitude towards life science new curriculum of trained teachers are insignificantly different from non-trained teachers. In the same way, the present study also indicates that training does not play any crucial role in construction of teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science.

Conclusion

The study intended to know students' and teachers' attitude towards new curriculum of life science at secondary level in West Bengal. This study ultimately found that students and school teachers of West Bengal possess a moderate positive attitude towards new life science curriculum. The most interesting point among above findings was female students had better attitude towards life science new curriculum than male and on the other hand rural students have higher attitude towards life science new curriculum than the urban student. Another most important finding was male teacher possessed higher attitude towards new

curriculum of life science than female teachers, but location of school, academic qualification and training had no significant role to construct attitude of teachers towards new curriculum of life science.

Limitations of the study

The present study had some limitations which were as follows:

1. For reviewing about new curriculum evaluation, the books, journals and various Government reports were consulted as far as possible in respect to its availability.
2. The selection of schools for this study was not selected with strict randomization.
3. The schools were selected mainly from four districts (Nadia, North-24-parganas, Hooghly and Howrah) of West Bengal.
4. The sample size could have been expended including.....an earlier in data collection would have increased the time needed to more participants.
5. The participants represented a narrow range of ethnicity/ ages/etc.
6. Sample was limited to 100 students of class IX and 60 life science teachers.
7. The sample of this study was selected only from the Govt. aided Bengali medium schools of WBBSE.

References:

- Ashton, P., Webb, R., Doda, C. (1983) A study of teachers' sense of efficacy. (Final report: Executive summary). University of Florida, Gainesville, FL.
- Berman, P., McLaughlin, M. (1977) Federal programs supporting educational change, Vol. VII Factors affecting implementation and continuation. Rand Corporation, Santa Monica, CA.
- de Souza-Barros, S., & Elia, M. F. (1997). Physics teachers' attitudes: How do they affect the reality of the classroom models for change? In A. Tiberghien, E. L. Jossem, & J. Barojas (Eds.), *Connecting research in physics education with teacher education*. International Commission on Physics Education. Available online at www.physics.ohio-state.edu/tjossem/ICPE/TOC.html
- Dewey, J. (1902). *The child and the curriculum*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Dosanjh, M. (2015) Secondary school students' attitude towards life science, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, 2(5), 139-142.
- Evans, R. (2004, August). "The human side of change." Presentation to the Hawaii Preparatory Academy faculty, August 6, 2004. Kamuela, Hawaii.
- Henkel, M. & Kogan, M. (1999), Changes in curriculum and institutional structures, in C. Gellert, ed., 'Innovation and Adaptation in Higher Education', Jessica Kingsley Publ., 116 Pentonville Road, London N1 9JB, England, chapter 2.
- Hetland, L. (1996). "Understanding goals: Teaching the humanities for understanding in middle school." In M. S. Wiske (Chair), *Teaching for understanding: A framework in practice*. Symposium conducted at the annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association, New York City, New York. (ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED411179). http://scripts.mit.edu/~varun_ag/readinggroup/images/9/9c/Secondary_Education.pdf (25/05/2015, 4.05 pm)
- Jones, M. G., Howe, A., & Rua, M. J. (2000). Gender differences in students' experiences, interests, and attitudes toward science and scientists. *Science Education*, 84(2), 180-192.
- Keeves J., & Kotte, D. (1992). Disparities between the sexes in science education: 1970-84. In J. Keeves (Ed.), *The IEA study of science III*. New York: Pergamon, pp.141-164.

- Lasserre, C. (1989) Relationships between selected school context variables and teacher self-efficacy and self-confidence (Doctoral dissertation, University of New Orleans, 1989). Dissertation Abstracts International 51: pp. 02A-02A
- Ministry of Human Resource Development. *National policy on education*. New Delhi, Government of India, 1986.
- National Science Foundation. (1994). *Women, minorities, and persons with disabilities in science and engineering*. Washington, DC.
- Sen, V. (2012). *Notification No.849-SE(S)/ES/S/10M-64/II*. Government of West Bengal School Education Department (Secondary Branch), Bikash Bhaban, Bidhannagar, Kolkata.
- Shrigley, R. L. (1983) The attitude concept and science teaching. *Science Education* 67: pp. 425-442
- Westerback, M. E., Long, M. J. (1990) Science knowledge and the reduction of anxiety about teaching earth science in exemplary teachers as measured by the science teaching state-trait anxiety inventory. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching* 19: pp. 603-616

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